

L versus parity-L

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Abstract

A major complexity classes are L and $\oplus L$ (parity-L). A logarithmic space Turing machine has a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and some read/write work tapes. The work tapes may contain at most $O(\log n)$ symbols. L is the complexity class containing those decision problems that can be decided by a deterministic logarithmic space Turing machine. The complexity class $\oplus L$ has the same relation to L as $\oplus P$ does to P . Whether $L = \oplus L$ is a fundamental question that it is as important as it is unresolved. We prove there is a complete problem for $\oplus L$ that can be logarithmic space reduced to a problem in L . In this way, we demonstrate that $L = \oplus L$.

2012 ACM Subject Classification Theory of computation \rightarrow Complexity classes; Theory of computation \rightarrow Problems, reductions and completeness

Keywords and phrases complexity classes, logarithmic space, XOR-3SAT, XOR-2SAT, reduction

1 Results

► Definition 1. XOR-3SAT

INSTANCE: A natural number n and a Boolean formula ϕ that is the conjunctions of a set C of clauses c_1, \dots, c_m , where each c_i consists of the EXCLUSIVE OR (denoted \oplus) of three literals and ϕ contains n variables represented by a unique positive integer between 1 and n just similar to the DIMACS representation [3].

QUESTION: Is it the case that ϕ is satisfiable?

REMARKS: XOR-3SAT is complete for $\oplus L$ [2].

► Definition 2. XOR-2SAT

INSTANCE: A Boolean formula ψ that is the conjunctions of a set C of clauses c_1, \dots, c_m , where each c_i consists of the EXCLUSIVE OR (denoted \oplus) of two literals and the ψ variables are represented by a unique positive integer just similar to the DIMACS representation [3].

QUESTION: Is it the case that ψ is satisfiable?

REMARKS: XOR-2SAT is in L [1], [4].

A logarithmic space transducer is a Turing machine with a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and some read/write work tapes [5]. The work tapes must contain at most $O(\log n)$ symbols [5]. A logarithmic space transducer M computes a function $f : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$, where $f(w)$ is the string remaining on the output tape after M halts when it is started with w on its input tape [5]. We call f a logarithmic space computable function [5]. We say that a language $L_1 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is logarithmic space reducible to a language $L_2 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, written $L_1 \leq_l L_2$, if there exists a logarithmic space computable function $f : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$ such that for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$,

$$x \in L_1 \text{ if and only if } f(x) \in L_2.$$

► Theorem 3. $L = \oplus L$.

Proof. From the Definition 1, we assume that each variable in the Boolean formula ϕ of n variables in XOR-3SAT is represented by a unique positive integer between 1 and n . The negative literals are represented as the negative value of each variable value, such that the negative literal of the variable a is $-a$. In order to make the reduction, we need to create

the variables inside of a Boolean formula in *XOR-2SAT* and therefore, we use the function h such that

$$h(x) = \text{if } (x > 0) \text{ return } (2 \times x) \text{ else return } (-2 \times x + 1).$$

Moreover, from a tuple (x, y) of two integers, we denote the function g such that

$$g((x, y)) = \text{if } (x < y) \text{ return } (x, y) \text{ else return } (y, x)$$

where g sorts the elements of a tuple (x, y) of two integers. Furthermore, from a tuple (x, y) of two positive integers, we denote the function v such that

$$v((x, y)) = ((x + y)^2 + 3 * x + y) / 2$$

where v returns a unique integer for a tuple (x, y) of two positive integers. Finally, we denote a clause that contains n -integers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n as the function $c(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ just similar to the DIMACS representation [3]. The logarithmic space reduction is described in the pseudo code Algorithm 1.

In this reduction, we guarantee that creation of the variables through the function h . In addition, using the functions g and v , we create the literals into the clauses of the final formula ψ in *XOR-2SAT*. In the first step, we create four clauses in *XOR-4SAT* for each clause in ϕ introducing two new variables $p = n + 1$ and $q = n + 2$, where these total generated clauses are satisfied for some truth assignment if and only if the Boolean formula ϕ is satisfiable when the variables $p = n + 1$ and $q = n + 2$ take opposite values. Hence, we output three clauses that are satisfied for some truth assignment if and only if the four generated clauses are satisfied. Certainly, a clause $(x \oplus y \oplus z \oplus w)$ is satisfied for some truth assignment if and only if the clauses $(a_{x \oplus y} \oplus b_{z \oplus w})$, $(a_{x \oplus z} \oplus b_{y \oplus w})$ and $(a_{x \oplus w} \oplus b_{y \oplus z})$ are satisfied for the same truth assignment, where in this case x, y, z and w are literals and the variables $a_{x \oplus y}, b_{z \oplus w}, a_{x \oplus z}, b_{y \oplus w}, a_{x \oplus w}$ and $b_{y \oplus z}$ are equals to the values of $(x \oplus y), (z \oplus w), (x \oplus z), (y \oplus w), (x \oplus w)$ and $(y \oplus z)$, respectively. Note, that we use tuples and thus, for that reason, we need to output two additional clauses for each pair of variables including the introduced variables $p = n + 1$ and $q = n + 2$. For these two new clauses in the second step, we guarantee the appropriated assignment for a single variable in ϕ , which means that a literal should have the opposite value of its negation. We could affirm this, because of the clauses $(x \oplus j \oplus \neg x \oplus j)$ and $(x \oplus \neg j \oplus \neg x \oplus j)$ are always satisfied for any truth assignment, where \neg is the *NOT* Boolean function. Finally, in the third step, we guarantee the variables $p = n + 1$ and $q = n + 2$ could take opposite values just making the formula ϕ satisfiable from the first step. Actually, we can assure this, because of the clause $(p \oplus j \oplus q \oplus j)$ is satisfied for some truth assignment if and only if p and q take opposite values. In this way, we create a Boolean formula $\psi \in \text{XOR-2SAT}$ if and only if $\phi \in \text{XOR-3SAT}$. In general, the whole algorithm uses logarithmic space in the work tapes since the new Boolean formula is created in the output tape into a write-only way. Consequently, we obtain $\text{XOR-3SAT} \leq_l \text{XOR-2SAT}$. The single existence of a complete problem in $\oplus L$ that could be logarithmic space reduced to a problem in L is sufficient to show $L = \oplus L$. This work is implemented into a Project programmed in Scala from a GitHub repository [6]. ◀

References

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Algorithm 1 Logarithmic space reduction from *XOR-3SAT* to *XOR-2SAT*

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1: /*A natural number  $n$  and a Boolean formula  $\phi$  of an instance from XOR-3SAT*/
2: procedure REDUCTION( $n, \phi$ )
3:   /*Create two new variables*/
4:    $p \leftarrow n + 1$ 
5:    $q \leftarrow n + 2$ 
6:   /*First step: Iterate for the clauses in  $\phi$ */
7:   for all  $c(a, b, c) \in \phi$  do
8:     /*Convert the clause to four clauses in XOR-4SAT*/
9:      $S \leftarrow \{c(a, b, c, p), c(a, b, c, -q), c(-a, -b, -c, -p), c(-a, -b, -c, q)\}$ 
10:    for all  $c(x, y, z, w) \in S$  do
11:      output  $c(v(g((h(x), h(y))))), v(g((h(z), h(w))))$ )
12:      output  $c(v(g((h(x), h(z))))), v(g((h(y), h(w))))$ )
13:      output  $c(v(g((h(x), h(w))))), v(g((h(y), h(z))))$ )
14:    end for
15:  end for
16:  /*Second step: Iterate quadratically from 1 to  $n + 2$ */
17:  for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $q$  do
18:    for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $q$  do
19:      if  $i \neq j$  then
20:        output  $c(v(g((h(i), h(j))))), v(g((h(-i), h(j))))$ )
21:        output  $c(v(g((h(i), h(-j))))), v(g((h(-i), h(-j))))$ )
22:      end if
23:    end for
24:  end for
25:  /*Third step: The variable  $p$  takes the opposite value of  $q$ */
26:  for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
27:    output  $c(v(g((h(p), h(j))))), v(g((h(q), h(j))))$ )
28:    output  $c(v(g((h(p), h(-j))))), v(g((h(q), h(-j))))$ )
29:    output  $c(v(g((h(-p), h(j))))), v(g((h(-q), h(j))))$ )
30:    output  $c(v(g((h(-p), h(-j))))), v(g((h(-q), h(-j))))$ )
31:  end for
32: end procedure

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